

Appendices

Supplementary files: Experience of education in the international classroom-A systematic qualitative literature review study

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Appendix, table 1 : Included articles about teaching and learning experience in the international classroom.

Author/s- Date	Topic	Aim	Method	Sample-setting	Result*
Brunton et., al. 2014	Identifying factors that influence the learner empowerment of international students	Identify factors that influence the process of acculturation in an educational context	Mixed methodological study. Content analysis	133 students. New Zealand	Language barriers. Confusion as a result of different academic culture. Groupwork and exclusion of international students. Working harder.
Cruickshank, et., al. 2015	Increasing international and domestic student interaction through groupwork	Explores the use of group work strategies to increase student interaction and learning	Qualitative interview study.	6 academic staff. 14 international students. 2 local students. Australia	Language barrier. Groupwork benefit: social benefit, learning benefit (study subject and language). Unequal participation in group work. Hardworking
Davis. 2012	International postgraduate students' experiences of plagiarism education in the UK	Exploring the perceptions of staff and students at another UK university about the plagiarism definition	Qualitative interview study.	8 international students 8 tutors- UK	Different academic culture. Little information about academic writing style. Stereotype.
Evan, et., al. 2011	The experience of international nursing students studying for a PhD in the UK	Investigate the learning expectations and experiences of overseas doctoral nursing students in the UK	Qualitative study. Semi-structured interview	17 international nursing students. UK	Different academic culture: student centered learning independent learning student/teacher relationship. Challenges of academic writing and language barrier.

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Foster, et., al. 2012	Understanding Chinese Students' Learning Needs in Western Business Classrooms	Recognized tension experienced by teachers and students resulting from an increasingly internationalized university classroom	Qualitative study. Interview Focus group	Interview with university stakeholders. 4 focus group with Chinese international students(10-12 each) Canada	Different academic culture; group work; presentation; speak freely; student teacher relationship. Challenges of participation and presentation. Language barrier.
Gram, et., al. 2013	Chinese students making sense of problem-based Learning(PBL) and Western teaching	Explores the difficult times experienced by Chinese students in a PBL setting at a Danish University	Qualitative study- Interview	Chinese students in Denmark.	Challenges and opportunities of working in a group. Practice of asking critical questions. Confusion: new learning environment
Harrison et., al. 2010	Home higher education students' perspectives on 'internationalisation at home'	To explore the range of experiences undergone by home students (internationalization)	Qualitative study. Semi-structured Interview Focus group	60 students for Focus group. 40 students for interview. UK	Exclusion of international students. Exclusion of home students. Language barriers and its impact on group work and interaction. Negative stereotypes.

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Hughes, et., al. 2013	International students' experiences of informed learning	To gain varied insights into the students' experiences of informed learning	Qualitative method. Written reflection. Semi-structured Interview	18 written reflection and 11 international students. Australia	Different academic culture: Informed learning, student centered, interaction with teachers, different teaching method and writing style. Class discussion: inclusion, anxiety. Development.
Janjua, et., al. 2011	Learning Experiences and Academic Adjustment of International Students	Exploring the classroom issues based on the difference of learning experiences of the foreign students in a Pakistani University	Qualitative study. Structured interview.	103 students. 10 teachers- Pakistan	Different academic culture: separate campus, teaching method, from copy and pasting to critical thinking method, and group discussion. Language barrier.
Kerdchoochuen. 2011	Intercultural Classrooms' Tensions And Managing Strategies	Explore whether strategies native English-speaking teachers and Thai students use to manage the dialectical tensions in an intercultural classroom	Qualitative interview study	20 native English teachers. 20 Thai students. Thailand	Flexibility of international teachers. Academic culture: relationship and interaction between students and teachers.
Khozaei, et., al. 2014	Factors that affect the research progress of international PhD students from the Middle East	Understand the difficulties that these students face while conducting their research in a foreign country	Qualitative study- Unstructured interview	35 Middle Eastern PHD students in South East Asian university- India	Supervisor's impact (positive and negative impact in education) Academic writing (knowledge and language skill)

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Kim, et., al. 2014	Emerging culture of English-medium instruction in Korea: experiences of Korean and international students	Examine Korean and international students' experiences of taking subject courses at a Korean university	Mixed methodological study. Qualitative interview.	23 Korean students and 9 international students. Korea.	Language barrier and its negative impact on learning. student's interaction, group work. English lectures= show time for those with good English.
Kim. 2011	International graduate students' difficulties: graduate classes as a community of practices	Attempts to explore the factors that cause international graduate students to struggle and the ways in which they deal with such problems	Qualitative study. Interview. Observation.	5 International students. Observation of 14 students in a class. United States	Language barrier. Different academic culture: classroom participation, group discussion, lack of transparency about the objective of group work and group discussion; relationship between students and teachers, losing identity.
Kumi-Yeboah, et., al. 2014	Transformative Learning Experiences of International Graduate Students From Asian Countries	Investigates the transformative learning experiences of international graduate students from Asian countries	Mixed methodological study. Qualitative study. Interview	10 international students from Asia. United States	New teaching and learning style: classroom discussion, Language barrier.

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Mukmin et., al. 2013	International Graduate Students' Cross-Cultural Academic Engagement	Explore the lived experience of academic engagement of twelve Indonesian doctoral students attending an American graduate school	Qualitative study. Semi-structured interview	12 Indonesian doctoral students. United States	Work load and high expectation (Reading, homework and assignments)—lack of engagement to class discussion) Language barrier (listening, speaking, reading and writing): lack of confidence to give presentation and engage to group discussion. Different academic culture: passive learning, relationship with faculty and student.
Rienties, et., al. 2015	Potential in cross-cultural learning	Understanding of how international and host students develop social learning relations over time	Mixed method study. Qualitative interview	International classroom, 28 nationalities, UK	Advantage of group work. Learn from each other. Disadvantage of group work. Lack of communication. Language barrier.
Saravanananthu, et. al. 2014	Pedagogy to empower Chinese Learners to adapt to western learning circumstances	Examine whether pedagogical interventions could facilitate adaptation to deeper learning strategies	Semi-qualitative case-study. Semi-structured interview	Two Chinese students (longitudinal interviews—in total 4). Australia	Fear of classroom discussion. Language barrier: exclusion from group work, difficulties to understand lectures, lack of shared learning, challenge of essay writing.

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Sawir, 2011	Dealing with diversity in internationalized higher education institutions	Explores academic staff perspectives with regard to the presence of international students in their institutions	Qualitative study. Semi-structured interview	80 academic staff Australia	Adjustment of teaching. All students are the same. In addition to inherited standard. Aware of language barriers and cultural differences. Applying strategic pedagogical environment.
Shendan 2011	A holistic approach to international students	Examines the interplay between academic staff and international students with regard to developing a academic literacies at university	Qualitative-Semi-structured interview-questionnaire	22 international students (undergraduate and postgraduate), 17 academic staff Ireland	Struggling with academic writing (education system differences) Language matters (needs for more service) Challenge of group work (free riders)
Tait, et., al. 2010	Chinese Students' Perceptions of the Effects of Western University Examination Formats on their Learning	Examine how Chinese undergraduate students' perceptions of examination formats in a New Zealand university affected their approaches to learning	Mixed method- Qualitative interview	18 Chinese students in New Zealand.	Getting grade based on their language skills. Using memorization technique. Advantage of group work: getting feedback
Tang 2010	University lecturers' experiences with internationalisation	Investigation of the impact of internationalisation on university lecturers' ability to read and interact with their students	Qualitative interview study	20 academic staff, Denmark	Language and communication concern. Diversity issue: different classroom behavior, different qualification (lowering academic standard), different learning tradition, advantage of diversity.

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Tang et., al. 2013	An inclusive approach to international education	To develop the notion of international education	Qualitative study- semi structured interview	34 academic staff in five Danish faculties Denmark	Providing same opportunity for all students to use whatever knowledge they have. Convergence of multiple perspectives challenge the knowledge hegemony. Working comparatively. Emergent synergistic skills
Tang, et., al. 2012	Good teachers and deviant learners? The meeting of practices in university level international education	Impact of internationalization on university lecturers' practice	Qualitative study. Interview	36 academic staff. Denmark	Equal education regardless of students nationality: impact of experience and academic background. Different academic culture: the role of teachers and students (interaction). Different learning and teaching culture.
Tian, et., al. 2013	The role of feedback in cross-cultural learning	In-depth understanding of Chinese students' experiences in a British university	Qualitative longitudinal study. Case study. Interview	13 Chinese students. UK	Different academic culture: negative impact of formative feedback, student centered teaching, adjusting to the new learning environment, different writing style (citation issue).

Author/s-Date	Topic	Aim	Method	Sample-setting	Result*
Trahar, et., al. 2011	Experiences and perceptions of internationalisation in higher education in the UK	Interested to hear from people about their experiences and perceptions of being in an international environment	Qualitative study. Focus group.	31 academic staff, 19 international students, 13 home students. UK	Student interaction based on the ethnicity and their native language. Challenges of group work in the international environment.
Valdez. 2015	U.S. Higher Education Classroom Experiences of Undergraduate Chinese International Students	Undergraduate Chinese international students' perceptions about their classroom experiences in the United States institutions of higher education	Qualitative study. Interview	15 Chinese international students. United States	Different academic culture: discussion based teaching style. Relationship between teachers and students. Advantage of oral presentation and group work. Classroom participation and stress. Stereotype and discrimination: exclusion.
Wang, et., al. 2011	Chinese students adjusting to western approaches to teaching and learning	Study of students' own conceptualisation of their learning	Qualitative study- Ethnographic interview- observation	Taiwanese and Chinese students- UK	Linkage of internationalization and learning. Language barrier. Critical thinking: difficulties to criticize or ask questions.

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Wang 2012	Transformations of Chinese international students understood through a sense of wholeness	Explore Chinese international students' academic and personal transformation under the influences of formal education in schools and informal education outside of the classroom	Qualitative study. Semi-structured interview.	8 Chinese international students. Canada	L-anguage barrier. Different academic culture: from teacher centered and exam oriented environment to student-centered and research-oriented environment.
Yats, et., al. 2012	The meaning of silence in the international classroom	Gain insight from the perspective of Vietnamese students themselves into this perceived lack of participation in Australian university classrooms	Qualitative study. Semi-structured interview	10 Vietnamese postgraduate students. Study in Australian university-Australia	Education system and concept of academic argument (discussion) L-anguage barrier (lack of confidence/ interaction in class) Education system (teacher centered vs student centered)

*Interpretation of the result: Only from qualitative part of the study, and only the result related to learning and teaching in the international classroom.